

EXA4MIND

D1.2

Continuous Improvements of Architecture, and Release Management Process and System

BADW-LRZ

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Abstract

The EXA4MIND project builds a platform for Extreme Data Analytics, leveraging European supercomputing centres and best-of-breed data stores from SQL and noSQL databases over object stores to classical High-Performance-Computing backend file systems. The platform is to connect to the European data ecosystem with European Data Spaces, the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and EUDAT. The platform with its components, and in particular its core, the “Extreme Data Database”, need to be developed, released and deployed (or also published) in a well-coordinated manner. A formalisation of architectural improvement cycles, release management processes and deployment or publication processes is needed, but should not inhibit research work. This deliverable devises the necessary formalisms. It discusses our approach to categorise software products in modules and submodules, to manage individual submodule and entire module releases. Then, it describes our current modular and portable EXA4MIND architecture, explaining its concept, its parts and its usage in practice. The deliverable closes laying out our plan for handling architectural improvement cycles.

Keywords

EXA4MIND Architecture; Release Management; Continuous Improvement; EXA4MIND Platform; Extreme Data Database

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Dissemination Levels

PU Public Public, fully open, e.g. website

SEN Sensitive Confidential to EXA4MIND project and Commission Services

Deliverable Types

R Document, report (excluding periodic and final reports)

DEM Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC Websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER Software, technical diagrams, etc.

Table of Contents

- Executive Summary 8**
- 1 Introduction 9**
- 2 SCM and Categorisation/Cataloguing of Software in EXA4MIND 10**
 - 2.1 GitLab-based Agile Development and SCM Platform 10
 - 2.2 Modules and Submodules 10
 - 2.2.1 Structuring EXA4MIND Software Products 11
 - 2.2.2 Implications on Development – Coherence vs. Freedom 11
 - 2.2.3 Toolboxes as an Example Module; List of Modules and Submodules 11
- 3 Release management 12**
 - 3.1 Versioning of (Sub-)Modules 12
 - 3.2 Bringing the Submodule Versions Together: Module Releases 12
 - 3.3 Public vs. Private Modules 13
 - 3.4 Integrating, Deploying and/or Publishing Module Releases 14
- 4 Current EXA4MIND Architecture and Architectural Evolution Planning 14**
 - 4.1 EXA4MIND Architecture 14
 - 4.1.1 Module “Database and Object Store Instantiation Recipes” (from Task T2.2) 15
 - 4.1.2 Module “Toolboxes” (including Preprocessing Toolbox from Task 3.1) 16
 - 4.1.3 Module “AQIS” (from Task 3.2) 17
 - 4.1.4 Module “Compute” 18
 - 4.1.5 Future Modules – “Dataset Index, FAIR Support and Versioning” . . 19
 - 4.2 The “Portable Platform” Approach: EXA4MIND EDD in Supercomputing-Centre Environments 20
 - 4.2.1 Example Usage Scenario 1 – “Website for Advanced Data Querying and Data Augmentation” 20
 - 4.2.2 Example Usage Scenario 2 – “Data Mining with Advanced Queries and Dataset Publication on HPC Simulation Output” 22
 - 4.3 Planning of Architecture Updates 24
- 5 Conclusions 25**
- 6 References 26**

List of Figures

Figure 1	“Submodule-version-to-module-version” mapping table for the first release of the Toolboxes module (Milestone MS8, Month 14), as described in Subsection 3.2. The mapping table contains information on which sub-modules are to be published in each module release (cf. Subsections 3.3 and 3.4).	13
Figure 2	Architecture of the EXA4MIND Portable Platform as of 06/2024.	15
Figure 3	Usage Scenario “Website for Advanced Data Querying and Data Augmentation”. The part above the bold dashed line shows the architectural components (cf. Figure 2) used; the lower part shows the instantiated system as explained in the text. Note that the system diagram below the dashed line is simplified for a better overview, and thus excludes some components used (Query Inference for translating natural-language to SQL queries, Database Catalogue to manage connection between files and database parts; Airflow instance to call staging provider and post-processing/validation tools). In addition, the constant ingest of external weather station data into the PostgreSQL database – a moderately difficult task dealing with relatively low data volumes – is not further discussed here.	21
Figure 4	Usage Scenario “Data Mining with Advanced Queries and Dataset Publication on HPC Simulation Output”. The part above the bold dashed line shows the architectural components (cf. Figure 2) used; the lower part shows the instantiated system as explained in the text. Note that – analogous to Figure 3 – the lower part excludes components for simplifying the overview: The simulation generation and classifier training are not represented; Query Inference and Database Catalogue components, as well as post-processing and validation tools would be used as well as Airflow for staging control – as in the first usage scenario. In addition, the AQIS Cache Support would help with indexing and controlling the cache.	23
Figure 5	Architectural Improvement Cycle for Architecture Updates, as explained in the text.	25

List of Tables

No tables are given.

Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
AQIS	Advanced Query and Indexing System
CI	Continuous Integration
CD	Continuous Deployment
CRUD	Create, Read, Update, Delete (basic operations for persistent storage)
CWL	Common Workflow Language (Chapman et al. 2016)
DBMS	Database Management System
DOI	Digital Object Identifier (Technical Committee ISO/TC 46, SC 9 2022), one flavour of PID (see below)
EDD	Extreme Data Database
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable (Principles for RDM, Wilkinson et al. 2016)
HDF5	Hierarchical Data Format, version 5 (Folk et al. 2011)
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HPC	High Performance Computing
iRODS	Integrated Rule-Oriented Data System (Xu et al. 2017)
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
noSQL	no-Structured Query Language, i.e. not working with the Standard Query Language (cf. also SQL)
MS	Milestone
PID	Persistent Identifier
RDM	Research Data Management
REST	Representational State Transfer (Fielding 2000)
SCM	Source Code Management
SQL	Structured Query Language (Codd 1970)
Tx.y	Task x.y
TOSCA	Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications (Brogi, Soldani, and Wang 2014)
WP	Work Package

Table of Partners

Short Name	Partner
IT4I@VSB	IT4Innovations at VSB – Technical University of Ostrava (IT4Innovations) https://www.it4i.cz/en
BADW-LRZ	Leibniz Supercomputing Centre (LRZ) of the Bavarian Academy of Sciences and Humanities https://www.lrz.de/english/
METU	Middle East Technical University (METU) https://www.metu.edu.tr/
AUSTRALO	AUSTRALO Interinnov Marketing Lab https://www.australo.org/
EURAXENT	Euraxent https://www.linkedin.com/company/euraxent/
CVUT	Czech Institute of Informatics, Robotics and Cybernetics at the Czech Technical University (CIIRC CTU) https://www.ciirc.cvut.cz/
VALEO	Valeo https://www.valeo.com/en/czech-republic/
TERRAVIEW	Terraview https://www.terraview.co/
ALTRNATIV	Altrnativ https://altrnativ.com/?lang=en
VALEO.AI	Valeo.ai https://www.valeo.com/en/valeo-ai/

Executive Summary

The EXA4MIND project builds a platform for Extreme Data Analytics, leveraging European supercomputing centres and best-of-breed data stores from SQL and noSQL databases over object stores to classical High-Performance-Computing backend file systems. The platform is to connect to the European data ecosystem with European Data Spaces, the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and EUDAT. The EXA4MIND Platform with its components, and in particular its core, the “Extreme Data Database”, needs to be developed, released and deployed (or also published) in a well-coordinated manner.

Typically, in projects such as EXA4MIND, software (from infrastructure-as-code definitions over scripts to proper libraries) is developed, documented and first tested locally, building upon an initial architecture definition. However, the target has to be a coordinated development in shared repositories, well-defined releases, and well-defined code publication and system deployment procedures. EXA4MIND uses GitLab (<https://opencode.it4i.eu>) as its collaborative source-code-management platform and agile development environment. The collaboration has chosen to categorise its platform-software products in modules (e.g., the “Advanced Querying and Indexing System”, AQIS) and submodules (e.g., an adaptor within AQIS to PostgreSQL as a data management system) – according to which the group/repository structure in GitLab is organised. Each module (i.e., the corresponding GitLab group) contains a release-and-deployment repository, which assigns a list of submodule releases to a module release. This repository also contains pipelines (using the GitLab Continuous Integration / Deployment – CI/CD – framework) that deploy components as needed and publish relevant pieces of software.

This deliverable also presents our current platform architecture. It discusses current modules and submodules and then focuses on the concept of the “EXA4MIND EDD Portable Platform” by illustrating how our components are instantiated and used in practice. However, this architecture of EXA4MIND is not static; instead, it will evolve throughout the project, corresponding to a series of deliverables and milestones (D1.1 – requirements; MS1 – initial architecture; D1.4 – final architecture). Therefore, we envisage an architectural improvement cycle consisting of phases where *(i)* we collect new requirements and propose respective changes, *(ii)* we consolidate the architectural changes to be made, *(iii)* we document the new architecture (in particular with an updated architecture scheme), and *(iv)* the architectural changes shall – where needed – reflect in an updated module-submodule structure (accommodating, e.g., additional components, different interaction or attribution of components). We estimate one to three of these cycles *(ii)*-*(iv)* to be executed by the end of the project (where the exact number adapts to actual needs).

1 Introduction

A platform as being built in EXA4MIND requires proper and streamlined management of architectural improvements, software components and their releases, and deployment or code-publication actions. This helps to ensure proper definition and visibility of EXA4MIND’s “products” inside and outside the project, easy collaboration, and quality control. However, components such as the “Extreme Data Database” (EDD) with the “Advanced Querying and Indexing System” (AQIS) and its data stores (cf. D1.1 – EXA4MIND 2023), or the EXA4MIND Preprocessing Toolbox, are relatively complex products to which multiple partner organisations contribute. Research & development by the partners must not be hindered by inappropriately bureaucratic release processes, inadequate immersion or categorisation of software within the entire platform, or overly complicated development standards. As the development process is streamlined (including software categorisation, releases, deployment, and publication methods), the focus also has to go back to the overall architecture, which has to see appropriate periodic improvements and thus provide up-to-date high-level guidance for the development of the components.

In this deliverable, we describe EXA4MIND’s efforts to handle architecture and release planning, as well as coordination of releases, deployments and software publication in our environment where pieces of software (from infrastructure-as-code definitions over scripts to proper libraries) are developed by different teams, with different speeds and methods. We focus on the following aspects in the Sections 2-4 below:

- ◆ First of all, in Section 2, we describe source-code management (SCM) in GitLab under IT4I@VSB management¹ (cf. e.g. Van Baarsen 2014) and the group/repository structure generated there, based on our categorisation of EXA4MIND code products in submodules and modules.
- ◆ We then discuss deeper aspects of release management, including versioning schemes, handling of module releases, and deployment or publication of the products (Section 3).
- ◆ Section 4 showcases our current EXA4MIND Platform architecture, and comments on our plans for architectural improvements and its connection to the DoA and the release works.

Section 5, finally, concludes the deliverable, commenting also on its context in terms of milestones such as MS1 – initial architecture (M9) / MS2 – agile development environment (M14) and other EXA4MIND deliverables, such as D1.1 – architecture requirements (EXA4MIND 2023) / D1.4 – final architecture to be completed in M36.

¹EXA4MIND project GitLab repository : <https://opencode.it4i.eu>

2 SCM and Categorisation/Cataloguing of Software in EXA4MIND

Source Codes in EXA4MIND are managed with the help of the agile-development and SCM platform GitLab. This platform can also execute customised “GitLab CI” (Van Baarsen 2014) pipelines defined in a code repository and triggered by general special commits. We describe this system further in Section 2.1. However, a proper management of source-code-centric products requires not only an SCM platform but, even more so, a structured usage of it. Thus, the platform components have been structured (following the the initial architecture as reported in Deliverable D1.1 (EXA4MIND 2023, Fig. 7) into so-called modules and submodules, as will be discussed in Section 2.2.

2.1 GitLab-based Agile Development and SCM Platform

IT4I@VSB has been providing their GitLab-based SCM platform (EXA4MIND project repository –footnote 1, Page 9) to the project, where appropriate access to project members was ensured, accepting federated identities through B2ACCESS (EUDAT CDI 2024a) and MyAccessID (GÉANT Project and Association 2022). This platform does not only offer git-based SCM, but also management tools for software development processes (issue tracker, issue board, fine-grained and role-based access management, etc.).

In addition, GitLab features a “GitLab CI/CD” functionality to help implement continuous integration and deployment. YAML-based (Ben-Kiki, Evans, and Net 2021) “GitLab CI scripts” are run on commits (where one can select, e.g., only tagged commits or commits belonging to a release). This functionality relies on external containers or machines as pipeline “runners” and enables the execution of arbitrary code while maintaining simplified access to the repositories from pipeline tasks and enabling pipeline tasks to connect to the outside as foreseen from the infrastructure where the runner(s) is/are installed.

Further noteworthy features of GitLab – which may serve EXA4MIND in the future – are a container registry, which enables the user to manage and offer containerised software products, and the capability to serve html-based web pages directly from GitLab repositories (GitLab Pages).

2.2 Modules and Submodules

Structuring the software products of EXA4MIND within the SCM platform is paramount for reflecting the architecture in the development processes and for enabling appropriate release management. Below, we explain our structural concept of modules and submodules, comment on the freedom and coherence this model provides for code development, and lay out an example.

2.2.1 Structuring EXA4MIND Software Products

We have devised a structure of modules and submodules for our codebase. In this structure, modules are major components of the architecture. They are building blocks stably ascribed a functionality, such as AQIS (cf. Deliverable D3.1, EXA4MIND 2024a) or our toolboxes including the Preprocessing Toolbox. The modules contain submodules, which are individual pieces of software. While the submodules are maintained as git repositories, modules correspond to a GitLab group that the submodule repositories belong to.

A GitLab group of a module can also contain other GitLab groups (“submodule groups”) which contain a part of the submodules, thematically grouping them together.

2.2.2 Implications on Development – Coherence vs. Freedom

The module concept reflects the coherent EXA4MIND architecture and, with it, the overall direction of the project’s developments. The modules integrate submodules developed by one or a few individuals in a self-guided manner. Thus, developers from the various partner organisations are free to bring their development model into the project, with the only obligation to sensibly define releases for their pieces of software (cf. Section 3). Module releases are then realised by mapping version/release numbers of these individual software products to a module release number and executing necessary integration-test, deployment, or publication pipelines (cf. Section 3.4) on a tagged-release commit to a “release and deployment” repository of a module (cf. Section 3.2).

2.2.3 Toolboxes as an Example Module; List of Modules and Submodules

The EXA4MIND Toolboxes (with a first version of the *preprocessing toolbox* developed as Milestone MS8) can serve as a typical example for an EXA4MIND module. The module group is hosted under platform/toolboxes in the development group on EXA4MIND project repository (see footnote 1, Page 9). It contains the following submodule repositories in its first release:

- ◆ WP4 - Simulation Output to RDBMS (Relational DBMS),
- ◆ WP5 - Data Check,
- ◆ WP6 Viticulture - CSV To RDBMS,
- ◆ WP6 Viticulture - Featurefilter On File,
- ◆ WP6 Viticulture - FolderToDB,
- ◆ WP6 Viticulture - JSON to MongoDB (cf. Plugge, Hawkins, and Membrey 2010).

In addition, it contains a “ReleaseAndDeployment” repository, which defines the mapping of the submodule to module releases (as will be explained in Section 3.2) and contains pipelines for deployment or code publication (cf. Section 3.4).

The first platform release will comprise a release of the Toolboxes Module, the AQIS Module, the Compute Module, and the Database Instantiation Recipes Module [which allow for a systematic and uniform deployment of DBMS of the EDD on target infrastructures such as the IaaS (cf. Prodan and Ostermann 2009) Clouds or Kubernetes (Linux Foundation, Kubernetes Authors 2024) clusters at IT4I@VSB and BADW-LRZ]. The list of modules and submodules released (see Section 4.1 for the current status) can always be retrieved from the platform group listing and the module “ReleAsEAndDeploYment” repositories. Further modules will be defined and consolidated in the future (see Section 4.1.5 below).

3 Release management

Based on the repository structure discussed above, release management is defined where module releases are envisaged to take place every couple of months. Also, if their release date or version differs, our modules are expected to be usable, in addition to each other, in an integrated workflow due to sufficiently stable and lean interfaces.

Each module release collects appropriately versioned (see Subsection 3.1 below) individual software products (submodules) according to a “submodule-version-to-module-version” mapping table inside the module’s “ReleAsEAndDeploYment” repository (see Subsection 3.2). The “ReleAsEAndDeploYment” repository can also contain a pipeline that executes integration tests and publishes (for public module versions – see Subsection 3.3) or deploys the module (see Subsection 3.4). The integration tests ensure the compatibility of the various submodule-release versions in a module release.

3.1 Versioning of (Sub-)Modules

Modules and submodules undergo a 3-group semantic versioning (Preston-Werner 2013). A corresponding version number looks like:

$$n_{\text{major}} \cdot n_{\text{minor}} \cdot n_{\text{patch}}$$

n_{major} is changed if there is a new version of the (sub-)module where there is no backward compatibility of interfaces and usage modes. For new features, n_{minor} is incremented. Bug fixes are represented by an increased n_{patch} .

3.2 Bringing the Submodule Versions Together: Module Releases

Module releases are created by assigning submodule release versions (created via the GitLab release mechanism) to a module release version in the “submodule-version-to-module-version” mapping table inside the module’s “ReleAsEAndDeploYment” repository, as mentioned above. Every EXA4MIND module contains such a repository. After fixing the mapping, “ReleAsEAndDeploYment” repository itself is released, thus

Module Release	Submodule Name	Submodule Release for inclusion	Link to Submodule Repository	Description of Functionality	Public (N=no/not yet, Y=yes)
1.0.0	WP4 - simulation output to RDBMS	1.0.0	https://opencode.it4i.eu/exa4mind-private/platform/preprocessing-toolbox/wp4-simulation-output-to-rdbms	ingests WP4 simulation output to relational DBMS	
	WP5 - data check	1.0.0	https://opencode.it4i.eu/exa4mind-private/platform/preprocessing-toolbox/wp5-data-check	checks WP5 data	N
	WP6 Viticulture - CSV to RDBMS -	1.0.0	https://opencode.it4i.eu/exa4mind-private/platform/preprocessing-toolbox/wp6-viticulture-csv-to-rdbms	ingests data in CSV format into DBMS for WP6-Viticulture application case	N
	WP6 Viticulture - featurefilter on file -	1.0.0	https://opencode.it4i.eu/exa4mind-private/platform/preprocessing-toolbox/wp6-viticulture-featurefilter-on-file	filters CSV data according to certain features for WP6-Viticulture application case	N
	WP6 Viticulture - folder to DB	1.0.0	https://opencode.it4i.eu/exa4mind-private/platform/preprocessing-toolbox/wp6-viticulture-folder-to-db	converts an entire data folder from Terraview to a database	N
	WP6 Viticulture - JSON to MongoDB	1.0.0	https://opencode.it4i.eu/exa4mind-private/platform/preprocessing-toolbox/wp6-viticulture-json-to-mongodb	ingests data in JSON format into DBMS for WP6-Viticulture application case	N
...	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd	

Figure 1: “Submodule-version-to-module-version” mapping table for the first release of the Toolboxes module (Milestone MS8, Month 14), as described in Subsection 3.2. The mapping table contains information on which submodules are to be published in each module release (cf. Subsections 3.3 and 3.4).

creating a module release. The repository release triggers a GitLab-CI pipeline (cf. Section 3.4) with final integration tests (as necessary) as well as deployment and/or publication actions as we describe in the following. Figure 1 shows an example mapping table for the Toolboxes module.

3.3 Public vs. Private Modules

EXA4MIND works towards a Technology Readiness Level of 5 as an overall target. This implies that first development versions of submodules may be very experimental and/or immature. Thus, we develop all (sub-)modules in a “EXA4MIND develop-

ment” group within EXA4MIND project repository (see footnote 1, Page 9), and declare submodule releases public as soon as appropriate. This also allows our enterprise partners to bring submodules into EXA4MIND which contain non-public intellectual property of their companies.

As our target is an easy and comprehensive open-source publication of most of our codes, we are implementing an automatism (via the respective pipelines of the “ReleaseAndDeployment” repository) to publish codes as soon as marked as public in the last column of the submodule-version-to-module-version mapping table (cf. Figure 1). The respective repositories are then forked into the “EXA4MIND public” group on EXA4MIND project repository (see footnote 1, Page 9), open to the entire internet.

3.4 Integrating, Deploying and/or Publishing Module Releases

GitLab-CI gives us an easy possibility to integrate and deploy and/or publish our module releases. On a release commit in the “ReleaseAndDeployment” repository of any module, a module-specific pipeline will run integration-test, deployment and/or code-publication tasks as described above; and the final module release tag will only be assigned after a successful (dummy) run before. The necessary GitLab-runner (cf. Van Baarsen 2014) infrastructure components have been collaboratively prepared and deployed within Tasks 1.2 and 1.3 (cf. Milestone MS2); they also serve continuous benchmarking tasks.

4 Current EXA4MIND Architecture and Architectural Evolution Planning

Since the project start, the EXA4MIND architecture has had some evolution, and we lay out the ideas behind it and its current status in Subsection 4.1. Subsection 4.2 explains our “portable platform” concept, illustrating how our architectural components can flexibly be instantiated in our supercomputing-centre environments depending on the application. Having all this described, we discuss our procedure for further architecture updates (Section 4.3, where we expect one to three significant updates in the remaining project runtime. These updates correspond to a somewhat “agile” development strategy, with architecture updates reflecting in EXA4MIND milestones and deliverables (D1.1 – requirements – EXA4MIND 2023; MS1 – initial architecture; D1.4 – final architecture).

4.1 EXA4MIND Architecture

Figure 2 shows the current version of the EXA4MIND architecture diagram. The most recent structural updates in the EXA4MIND architecture have focused on the AQIS concept and its integration with the EDD and all EXA4MIND components. On the one

Figure 2: Architecture of the EXA4MIND Portable Platform as of 06/2024.

hand, the concept corresponds well to the initial, coarser architecture concept (cf. Fig. 7 in D1.1 – EXA4MIND 2023). On the other hand, specific components and their interaction have evolved strongly in the co-design process with the application cases. This involves an integration of application-case software (cf. Deliverables D4.1, D5.1, D6.1, D6.3 – EXA4MIND 2024b; EXA4MIND 2024c; EXA4MIND 2024d; EXA4MIND 2024e) into our architecture as appropriate, as well as making sure that the application cases use the EXA4MIND Platform components wherever it fits their purpose. Thus, the platform is constantly put to the test and improved upon.

In the following Subsections (4.1.1–4.1.3), we discuss the functional elements (modules – the outer boxes in Figure 2), focusing on their scope and purpose and on their role in fulfilling the requirements collected in Deliverable D1.1. The flexible deployment of combinations of these modules and submodules will be discussed further below as a part of Subsection 4.2. All modules and submodules described are part of the EDD, except for the “Compute” module and the future module “Dataset Index, FAIR Support and Versioning”(cf. Wilkinson et al. 2016) which pertain to connectivity from the EDD.

4.1.1 Module “Database and Object Store Instantiation Recipes” (from Task T2.2)

This module (corresponding to the lowermost, blue box in Figure 2) makes sure that the backend data systems we need for our Extreme Data Analytics workflows can be flexibly deployed or instantiated. It consists of recipes (submodules) generated

within Task 2.2, allowing us to instantiate the following database management systems and object-storage systems (cf. Stonebraker and Rowe 1986; Plugge, Hawkins, and Membrey 2010; Gormley and Tong 2015; Redis Labs 2024; Taipalus 2024; Corti et al. 2014; Xu et al. 2017; MinIO 2024):

- ◆ PostgreSQL,
- ◆ MongoDB,
- ◆ Elasticsearch (or the fork OpenSearch),
- ◆ Redis (or the fork Valkey),
- ◆ PostgreSQL + pgvector,
- ◆ PostgreSQL + PostGIS,
- ◆ iRODS,
- ◆ S3.

The formalisation of these recipes depends on the system to be deployed and the deployment target (e.g., IaaS Cloud, Kubernetes Cluster). In principle, everything from a (complete, tested) HowTo to a fully-fledged deployment pipeline is acceptable; however, we clearly envisage the following infrastructure-as-code approaches (cf. Berton 2023):

- ◆ *Ansible* scripts for system instantiation on IT4I@VSB's and BADW-LRZ's IaaS Cloud (based on OpenStack or VSphere) – and, in very rare or experimental cases – deployment on HPC systems; these recipes are currently in the making;
- ◆ *Helm* charts and/or operators for deployment on Kubernetes clusters, where we have a fairly complete set available.

After execution, we envisage the recipes to feed back the data required by the AQIS data system adaptor to connect. By providing a safe and convenient way to offer a range of storage schemes for the different application cases, the module helps to address the requirements **R2** (support for various types of data), **R6** (support for different DB technologies), **R7** (efficient query execution) and **R12** (support for advanced querying on large data collections) as collected in Deliverable D1.1 (EXA4MIND 2023).

4.1.2 Module “Toolboxes” (including Preprocessing Toolbox from Task 3.1)

Toolboxes (see red box in Figure 2 on left hand) are sets of flexibly usable standalone tools within EXA4MIND. They fall into three categories (**submodule groups**) as we can foresee as of mid 2024:

- ◆ Preprocessing Tools – these tools have been prepared within Task 3.1 as “Pre-processing Toolbox” first released with Milestone MS8 (cf. 2.2).

- ◆ Data Validation – these tools serve to check and validate data against quality or integrity criteria after production or data transfer. With MS8, one validation submodule (WP5 - data check) has been integrated into the toolbox, and further tools are to be integrated.
- ◆ AI Toolbox – contains AI and Machine Learning algorithms and models of interest to EXA4MIND as a whole or to several application cases. Note that AI models related to natural-language query are not part of this toolbox but of AQIS (see below).

The preprocessing and validation tools serve to fulfil the formal requirements **R1** (data import capability), **R2** (support for various types of data), **R3** (support for different protocols including preprocessing). They can also implement encryption or compression mechanisms, addressing the requirements **R4** (data encryption) and **R5** (data compression). The number of preprocessing tools supplied is tracked with KPI 2.1 from the DoA.

4.1.3 Module “AQIS” (from Task 3.2)

The “AQIS” module and its architecture, as a core innovative development in EXA4MIND (by Task 3.2), are further described in its own Deliverable (D3.1) and take a central role in the architecture (cf. Figure 2, yellow box). Therefore, we only give a **short account of the submodule groups and their functionalities** here.

The objective of creating AQIS is to provide a unified, advanced query and fast-data-retrieval interface to our data-system backends. AQIS should allow for

- ◆ natural-language queries (requirement **R11** from Deliverable D1.1, cf. EXA4MIND 2023);
- ◆ queries to two or more backend systems with interlinked or otherwise related data (e.g. database with data with file pointers to an object store), and for advanced extreme data queries in general (**R12**);
- ◆ accelerating data retrieval by caching and indexing; and for
- ◆ its submodules being called/executed directly or via a REST (Fielding 2000) API.

Apache Airflow (The Apache Software Foundation 2024) was chosen as an intra-AQIS orchestrator to implement complex queries and data processing/AI pipelines involving data querying. The AQIS instance of Airflow can then, e.g., infer a SQL query from a natural-language input – calling the query-translation/inference submodule, hand over the query to the database, and stage the result wherever it is needed for further evaluation (or open a data-streaming endpoint).

The submodule groups of AQIS are as follows:

- ◆ “Workflow Catalogue”: supplies different examples and basic-functionality workflows for queries.
- ◆ “Query Inference”: contains trained models for translating natural-language queries into DBMS queries or data-access commands for files.

- ◆ “Providers - Data System Adaptors”: this submodule group collects different Airflow providers for addressing the various data backends that EXA4MIND uses, supporting connection/disconnection and CRUD operations.
- ◆ Submodule group “Interface Layer” (being designed): Besides the possibility of locally starting AQIS workflows via direct Python calls or similar APIs, we have to accommodate the scenario where AQIS is called from a remote system (e.g. data analytics website). This is made possible by providing an appropriate REST API.
- ◆ Further submodule groups being designed: A “Dataset Catalogue” will contain information on data distributed over various data systems or data-system instances, enabling common queries. Caching will be supported by appropriate submodules. Last but not least, the “AQIS Query Workflow Definition” submodule group aims to supply converters and tools for workflow definition, making it possible to run workflows not only in the form of Airflow scripts: our plan is to evaluate also the possibility to describe workflows in TOSCA (Brogi, Soldani, and Wang 2014) or CWL (Chapman et al. 2016).

All submodules with scripted functionality aim at implementing this functionality with Airflow, be it, e.g., a pipeline with typical Extract-Transform-Load pattern or a natural-language query. Thus, many functionalities of AQIS are implemented as Airflow operators (cf. also Deliverable D3.1 – EXA4MIND 2024a), grouped within providers (as, e.g., the data system adaptors).

In particular, the Workflow Catalogue and Data System Adaptors help to fulfil the requirements **R2** (support for various types of data), **R6** (support for different DB technologies), and **R7** (efficient query execution) of Deliverable D1.1 (EXA4MIND 2023). As already stated above, AQIS is essential for fulfilling **R11** and **R12**.

AQIS and its appropriate Airflow and API instances can be deployed temporarily on relevant computing infrastructure or as a (semi-)permanent service, depending on the application (cf. Section 4.2).

4.1.4 Module “Compute”

The module “Compute” (Figure 2, right-hand side – violet box) consists mainly of Airflow providers:

- ◆ to address heterogeneous computing systems (submodule group “HPC/Cloud/AI Systems Access”), making appropriate use of the HEAppE middleware (Svaton et al. 2019), and
- ◆ to stage or stream data between these systems (submodule group “Data Movement”, addressing requirement **R8** – data staging – from Deliverable D1.1, as well as **R3** – support for different protocols including preprocessing).

These providers have been developed for the LEXIS Platform² (Golasowski et al. 2022; Munke et al. 2022) and are modified as needed for use in EXA4MIND. Typically, they enable us to address LEXIS data-management and computing backends

²The first version of this platform was developed in the H2020 LEXIS project, GA #825532.

directly. The idea of using these providers not only creates synergies between the EXA4MIND project and the LEXIS Platform but also helps in the future integration of the EXA4MIND EDD in LEXIS workflows. LEXIS workflows can call and use EXA4MIND modules, which in turn address supercomputing backends via the LEXIS providers – supplying, e.g., solutions to authentication and connectivity problems in supercomputing environments. Together with the architectural adaptations of the LEXIS Platform to EXA4MIND and the convergence towards Airflow as an orchestration tool on various (front- to back-end levels throughout LEXIS and EXA4MIND), this promises an optimum environment to execute complex, cross-system data-driven workflows in the second half of the project.

The providers, together with some additional scripting, will also allow for offloading AQIS inference tasks to HPC systems. All in all, the module fundamentally supports the aims of EXA4MIND and in particular the more compute and data-heavy tasks within the application cases, helping to address all requirements within Deliverable D1.1 (EXA4MIND 2023) without any particular overemphasis.

The module thematically includes the LEXIS Platform capabilities, which EXA4MIND uses to orchestrate computing jobs across various computing backends from HPC over Cloud or Kubernetes systems to specialized hardware for AI.

4.1.5 Future Modules – “Dataset Index, FAIR Support and Versioning”

With Task 2.4 officially starting in the middle of 2024, the module “Dataset Index, FAIR Support and Versioning” will be created. This module first builds upon an existing dataset index in LEXIS as a seed for the “Dataset Indexing, Versioning, and FAIR support” submodule (or submodule group). It fulfils core tasks to enable a data publication from the EXA4MIND Platform according to the FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016) of modern RDM.

The index maps persistent identifiers (B2HANDLES or prospectively DOIs – EUDAT CDI 2024b; Technical Committee ISO/TC 46, SC 9 2022) and basic (at least DataCite- and DCAT-compliant) metadata to data locations, retrieval endpoints and commands (e.g. SQL endpoint and query; file system endpoint and path) for all significant datasets in EXA4MIND. Later, this index may be augmented by a versioned dataset index. A small resolver application (submodule “DOI / Handle / Version Resolution”) serves to redirect data requests – based on B2HANDLES or DOIs – to the right data endpoint or landing page. These functionalities help to address the requirements **R9** (metadata ingestion support, support for FAIR data, reproducibility and trust) and **R10** (support for versioning and handling large datasets) from Deliverable D1.1 (EXA4MIND 2023).

This “FAIR and versioning engine” is complemented by an interface layer (submodule group “External Connectors and Data Adaptors”). We will provide an InvenioRDM (cf. Bardi et al. 2023) instance on top of our dataset index, providing landing pages and an OAI-PMH (Lagoze et al. 2015) interface. Furthermore, we will not only maintain interfacing with EUDAT (Lecarpentier et al. 2013) as already in LEXIS (cf. also Deliverable D7.3 – EXA4MIND 2024f), but aim to interface with the European Data Spaces via an appropriate connector (most likely based on the Eclipse Dataspace Components, EDC – cf. Dam et al. 2023). To this end, ample research on the standards we have to fulfil has been conducted as part of Task 7.4 (see Deliverable D7.3 – EXA4MIND 2024f)

in collaboration with WP2.

Further future modules may be defined with new revisions of the architecture.

4.2 The “Portable Platform” Approach: EXA4MIND EDD in Supercomputing-Centre Environments

Perhaps “the” Key Exploitable asset resulting from the EXA4MIND project is clearly the “EXA4MIND EDD Portable Platform”. While we have extensively laid out the platform architecture and its components above, we have not yet discussed the practical usage or deployment of the platform in the different application cases. In order to make this aspect substantially clearer and explain what we mean by a “Portable Platform”, we illustrate the usage of the platform in two artificial application scenarios (Sub-sections 4.2.1 and 4.2.1) below. These scenarios shall convey fundamental principles of EXA4MIND (flexible component-wise usage of the platform; instantiation on the best-suited backends from Kubernetes to HPC clusters; temporary vs. service-like instantiation; etc.), while details and specialties of the platform utilisation in the use cases are left to current and future deliverables of WP4-WP6.

4.2.1 Example Usage Scenario 1 – “Website for Advanced Data Querying and Data Augmentation”

In our scenario 1, a research group would like to offer a website where the users can browse and query a massive weather simulation dataset and compare it to local weather station data. This scenario relates to the requirements of the WP4 Scientific Application Case and WP6 Altrnativ SME Application Case.

On the website to be provided, the user can retrieve a regional weather map under certain assumptions (e.g. initial conditions) and measured data for a number of weather stations in the big cities. While the weather data are stored as files in a user-defined format, the weather station timeseries data are available in a PostgreSQL database. The website gives a few special (“expert”) users the opportunity to augment the original weather simulation dataset, triggering simulation runs (based, e.g., on different initial conditions or microphysics assumptions) on an HPC cluster.

System instantiation. Figure 3 shows how the scenario can be realised using the EXA4MIND Portable Platform. Individual components are selected (upper part of Figure 3) and deployed to the most appropriate systems (part of Figure 3 below the dashed line). The research group deploys its website (lower left corner of Figure 3) on a standard web hosting service. In order to retrieve weather data maps and weather-station data for display, the website sends natural language requests to the REST API of AQIS, which, for this use case, is instantiated as a longer-term service on a virtual machine in an IaaS cloud. Via the appropriate data-system adaptor providers, the PostgreSQL database (deployed on a Kubernetes cluster with our recipes) and the S3 storage for the weather-simulation files are addressed. The augmentation of the simulation datasets with new simulations is realised by the website addressing HEAppE (Svaton et al. 2019) to trigger parametrised HPC jobs. A “cron job” on a Kubernetes cluster regularly runs a set of pre-processing, data validation, and staging

Figure 3: Usage Scenario “Website for Advanced Data Querying and Data Augmentation”. The part **above the bold dashed line** shows the architectural components (cf. Figure 2) used; the **lower part** shows the instantiated system as explained in the text.

Note that the system diagram below the dashed line is simplified for a better overview, and thus excludes some components used (Query Inference for translating natural-language to SQL queries, Database Catalogue to manage connection between files and database parts; Airflow instance to call staging provider and postprocessing/validation tools). In addition, the constant ingest of external weather station data into the PostgreSQL database – a moderately difficult task dealing with relatively low data volumes – is not further discussed here.

tasks (relying on EXA4MIND as tools) on new simulation outputs in order to ingest them in the S3 storage.

Backend usage at supercomputing centres. IT4I@VSB and BADW-LRZ provide the entire service portfolio (web spaces, HPC clusters, IaaS-Cloud infrastructure on premises, Kubernetes clusters, storage) in order to execute the deployment as described above. Nonetheless, one could, e.g., envisage the usage of public (commercial) cloud infrastructure for parts of the deployment as well - as the EXA4MIND components are not specifically tailored for a lock-in to one back-end infrastructure.

Further improvement potential through EXA4MIND. Having accommodated the usage scenario, we would envisage a further co-design evolution of the system devised. The weather station data might be extended with a massive geolocated grid of simulated timeseries. To facilitate efficient queries across these data, specialised DBMS or DBMS flavours such as TimescaleDB (Timescale Inc. 2024) or PostGIS (Corti et al.

2014) may be utilised. Also, the user-defined simulation files should be stored in a standard format (e.g. NetCDF – Rew and Davis 1990), readily accessible via an Airflow provider in EXA4MIND. This also gives the opportunity to annotate data with appropriate metadata (already within NetCDF) for FAIR data publication.

4.2.2 Example Usage Scenario 2 – “Data Mining with Advanced Queries and Dataset Publication on HPC Simulation Output”

For our second scenario, we imagine astrophysics experts having done cosmological HPC simulations with the LEXIS Platform and having stored the data as HDF5 files on the LEXIS Distributed Data Infrastructure (based on iRODS/EUDAT-B2SAFE).

They would now like to automatically annotate their simulation outcome (3-D density structure, etc., with astrophysical objects). This experiment will serve as an evaluation of the astrophysical properties and astrophysical object classification in the simulations and an exploration of the capabilities of such annotation methods. This scenario picks up requirements described by WP5 (VALEO/industry) and WP6 (Terraviva/SME) application cases. Both are expected to run heavy data-oriented AI training campaigns involving HPC, and the input datasets are selected based on AQIS queries and must be properly staged by the EXA4MIND toolbox.

First of all, the astrophysicists in our example run an existing “object detector” (segmenter from their earlier work) across their simulation data which isolates individual astrophysical objects (e.g. clusters of stars, galaxies, black holes) and devises bounding boxes around these objects. The code then stores basic object properties (such as mass, mean density, and extension) in a vector database. Then, the experts aim to train an AI model to classify astrophysical objects with a clustering algorithm. During AI model training, a large number of similarity searches are executed on the vector database; potentially also HDF5 (Folk et al. 2011) simulation data are accessed. With the full dataset, the model is later run for inference, and the results are statistically evaluated against / mapped to a classical astronomical object classification that was done by students.

After all this, the astrophysicists are testing model-data evaluation via natural language queries in order to identify the most exotic galaxy types for their next scientific paper. Finally, they will publish their earlier-produced raw simulation data together with the feature data in the vector database.

System instantiation. Figure 4 shows a possible implementation of this scenario, assuming that the simulation data already reside on iRODS as HDF5 files. While the principle of selecting platform components (upper part of Figure 4) and deploying them on the best-suited systems (lower part of Figure 4) remains the same as in our first scenario laid out above, the deployment itself is different. AQIS is temporarily instantiated for the computation execution time. It runs, together with the segmenter and classifier codes, in a Kubernetes environment, preferably on strong hardware with GPUs. Nonetheless, certain parts of training or inference may have to be offloaded to a GPU-accelerated HPC cluster, which is possible via our HPC/Cloud access provider from the LEXIS Platform. In particular, Airflow Executors may also be run on HPC clusters, where an Executor is a component of the Airflow that executes the actual code of the Task in a workflow.

Figure 4: Usage Scenario “Data Mining with Advanced Queries and Dataset Publication on HPC Simulation Output”. The part **above the bold dashed line** shows the architectural components (cf. Figure 2) used; the **lower part** shows the instantiated system as explained in the text. Note that – analogous to Figure 3 – the lower part excludes components for simplifying the overview: The simulation generation and classifier training are not represented; Query Inference and Database Catalogue components, as well as post-processing and validation tools would be used as well as Airflow for staging control – as in the first usage scenario. In addition, the AQIS Cache Support would help with indexing and controlling the cache.

The segmenter and classifier codes require access to the original data as HDF5 files as well as access to the vector database for the features to be stored (after segmenting) and then re-read. While the database may just be run within the Kubernetes cluster, the access to HDF5 files most probably requires AQIS to periodically stage relevant data from iRODS to a fast “cache” filesystem, as the iRODS middle-ware may prove a bottleneck or create latencies when attempting direct access from a high-performance code to data. AQIS accesses the data from the vector database (features) and HDF5 files (3-D density data) via the appropriate providers. In the later stages of the use case, AQIS will also serve natural-language query translation as required.

For the data publication, the HDF5 and PostgreSQL-pgvector data are assigned B2HANDLE PIDs and, in a few prominent cases, DOIs. The dataset catalogue holds the respective mapping and necessary metadata, and the resolver service to provide the datasets and/or landing pages is instantiated as a service on the Kubernetes cluster (see green boxes in the lower part of Figure 4).

Backend usage at supercomputing centres. The use case heavily relies on computing infrastructure with fast file systems and GPUs, as present at IT4I@VSB at BADW-LRZ. A specialty is that deployment in our scenario happens via Kubernetes, and only compute-intensive tasks are offloaded to classically managed HPC infrastructure. Permanent storage of the simulation outputs takes place on an iRODS/EUDAT-B2SAFE system (LEXIS Distributed Data Infrastructure) with a large permanent storage back-end (at BADW-LRZ, this would, e.g., be the “Data Science Storage”). By *portability* of the EXA4MIND Platform, we mean exactly this possibility to deploy our components on different back-end systems and with different lifetimes (as compared, e.g., to the first usage scenario), depending on the needs of the application.

Further improvement potential through EXA4MIND. After implementation as described, the EXA4MIND project would help such a use case mostly through a selection of the most optimum vector database, where several alternative systems to pgvector could be tested (e.g., Milvus – Milvus and Zilliz Devs 2024). Also, scientists have to devise a consistent FAIR data strategy, where the direct publication of data from the vector database (which may need a versioned database mirror) will be of great help.

4.3 Planning of Architecture Updates

Our architectural improvement cycle is shown in Figure 5. It consists of four phases where in (i) we collect new detailed requirements (gap analysis) and propose respective changes, in (ii) we consolidate the architectural changes to be made, in (iii) we document the new architecture (in particular with an updated architecture scheme), and (iv) the architectural are reflected in an updated module-submodule structure (with additional components, and/or different interaction or attribution of components). Before step (iv), a final release of the modules in the previous architecture is planned. A (new or initial) release of all modules specified in the new architecture version is then envisaged within four months after the architecture update. Modules that do not (yet) meet basic quality criteria (clearly defined interfaces, etc.) will be assigned a pre-release status, which they can work on, work with, and improve upon to facilitate a release within due time.

Figure 5: Architectural Improvement Cycle for Architecture Updates, as explained in the text.

5 Conclusions

In this deliverable, we have first devised a **formal framework to manage the evolution and development** of the EXA4MIND Platform from an abstract level down to the releases of individual parts of our code (submodules). The concept of the release of modules (building blocks within the architecture) as a collection of individual submodule releases gives the developers at all partner institutions the freedom they expect from a research-centric project while allowing for the platform’s systematic progress. Having built upon the experience of various partners from previous large (e.g., European) projects, we are confident that the scheme we have devised will stand the test of time with the architectural updates to come, as well as the releases of our platform modules. The release-management concept, making use of GitLab CI pipelines, also serves as a starting point for automating integration tests, deployment, and publication of modules as appropriate.

We have then concentrated on the **EXA4MIND architecture** in its current status, showing and discussing the EXA4MIND architecture diagram. After a discussion of current and future modules and submodules, we have focused on demonstrating how our “Portable Platform” is used in practice by instantiating and interfacing selected components on appropriate target systems at our supercomputing centres. We have motivated cycles of architectural improvements within the project run time and laid out our planning for the different phases of these architecture updates.

We are confident that our clear architecture and basic management ideas give us the right mix of guidance and necessary freedom for forefront innovation within our Extreme Data Platform in the making.

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